

FIRST RESULTS

STATUS
UPDATE ICOS
MATCH-UP
DATABASE
FOR S2 AND
S3

RESULTS FROM 3 NOTEBOOKS

1. FAPAR VALIDATION
2. LAI VALIDATION
3. SPATIAL REPRESENTATIVENESS ASSESSMENT

FAPAR VALIDATION WITH S2

- FAPAR from S2 Terrascope / S3 Copernicus product is derived in a specified radius around the tower (example cases: 50m/300m)
- FAPAR ground measurement is taken for the whole TA from *Meteo* file. Measurement at overpass time (~10:30 AM) is used for comparison for S2, aggregated weekly measurements at overpass time for S3.
- FAPAR ground is measured (*PPFD_BC_{in}* is included if measured at the site)

$$FAPAR = \frac{PPFD_{IN} - PPFD_{OUT} - PPFD_{BC_{IN}}}{PPFD_{IN}}$$

Findings

- General underestimation of ground FAPAR by satellite values
- Seasonality only apparent if *PPFD_BC_{in}* is included in the calculation of ground FAPAR
- Surface Albedo measurements could be used to substitute *PPFD_BC_{out}* measurements

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Hohes Holz

S2

S3

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Fontainebleau-Barbeau S2

S3

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Brasschaat

S2

S3

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/500M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Hyytalia

S2

S3

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Hyltemossa

S2

S3

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Tharandt

S2

S3

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Svarteberget

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Torgnon

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Bosco Fontana

* Calculation of FAPAR includes PPFD below canopy

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Maasmechelen

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Vielsalm

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Selhausen Juelich

EXAMPLES S2 VALIDATION WITH 50M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Auchencorth Moss

LAI VALIDATION WITH S2/S3

Version 1

- LAI from S2 Terrascope / S3 Copernicus product is derived in a specified radius around the tower (example cases: 50m/300m)
- Ground LAI/GAI is loaded from ICOS archive.
- Satellite measurements are interpolated to be matched with ground measurement

Version 2

- *LAI from S2 Terrascope is derived around CP/SP*
- Ground LAI/GAI is loaded from file (not available on ICOS site)
- Ground measurements are upscaled using S2 pixel information to Target Area and then compared to S3 LAI

LAI VALIDATION WITH S2/S3

Findings

S2

- General underestimation of ground LAI by satellite values
- More detailed information from CP/SP does not lead to significant improvement for S2 validation

S3

- Upscaling from S2 measurements leads to improvement of fit in most cases
- For upscaled values: underestimation of low LAI values, overestimation of high LAI values
- Very steep slopes, suggesting little variation in ground measurements

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

★ Fontainebleau-Barbeau

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

★ Voulundgaard

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Vielsalm

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/300M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Hyttiala

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

EXAMPLES S2/S3 VALIDATION WITH 50M/500M RADIUS AROUND THE TOWER

Hyltemossa

Circle around tower

S2

S3

Single measurement plots + upscaling

S2

S3

SPATIAL REPRESENTATIVES

Goal

- Assess whether a site is representative/homogeneous for S3 pixel size

Method

- Based on retrievals of biophysical variables (LAI/faPAR) from higher-resolution data (Sentinel-2), variogram functions are computed using different spatial and temporal thresholds.
- Four different geostatistical attributes are computed for different seasons during the year.
 - Relative coefficient of variation
 - Scale requirement index
 - Relative strength of the spatial correlation
 - Relative Proportion of Structural Variation
- Overall score for comparing stations

EXAMPLES OF SPATIAL REPRESENTATIVENESS

★ Svartberget (faPAR - summer)

Instrument set up and target area

Footprints

- RAD-PAR Quantum 4603
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q105120
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q105121
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114332
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114333
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114334
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114335
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114336
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114493
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114494
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114495
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114496
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114497
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114498
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q114499
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q52448
- RAD-PAR Quantum Q52452

Semi-variogram

EXAMPLES OF SPATIAL REPRESENTATIVENESS

Vielsalm (faPAR - summer)

Instrument set up and target area

Footprints

- RAD-PAR Quantum 43197
- RAD-PAR Quantum 43314
- RAD-PAR Quantum 43807
- RAD-PAR Quantum 44206
- RAD-PAR Quantum 50934

Semi-variogram

EXAMPLES OF SPATIAL REPRESENTATIVENESS

Selhausen Juelich (faPAR - summer)

Instrument set up and target area

Footprints

- RAD-PAR Quantum 100278
- RAD-PAR Quantum 100680
- RAD-PAR Quantum 23102

Semi-variogram

